

**The mysterious *Anelastes barbarus* P. H. Lucas, 1846 from Montenegro
(Coleoptera: Eucnemidae)**

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Abstract – *Anelastes barbarus* P. H. Lucas, 1846 (Coleoptera: Eucnemidae) is recorded for the first time from Montenegro.

Key words – false click beetles, new country record, rare species, faunistics

INTRODUCTION

During the vacation of the author a strange, dead elaterid-like beetle was found inside a building, under a light bulb at a campsite at the coast of Montenegro in September 2022. After taking the specimen out from the spider web and cleaning off the dirt from it, the insect was identified as a rare species of false click beetles (Coleoptera: Eucnemidae).

RESULTS

Anelastes barbarus P. H. Lucas, 1846
(Fig. 1)

Material examined – Montenegro, 2 km S Merdari, Rt. Veslo, Kamp Begovic, *Quercus ilex* grove, 42.366438°, 18.611409°, hand collected from spider web, 14.IX.2022, leg. T. Németh. The voucher specimen is deposited in the Coleoptera Collection of the Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest.

Remarks – First record from Montenegro. KOVALEV (2019) summarized the distribution of the species. The nearest known locality to Montenegro is the island of Hvar, Croatia, where specimens were collected at light, also in September (LUCHT 1990). Specimens of *Anelastes barbarus* are rare in collections, the life-history of the species is poorly known, and its immatures are unknown;

MUONA (2000) suggested that it may develop in the soil. The collecting area is a small but probably very old holm oak (*Quercus ilex* L. (Fagaceae)) grove near to the coast (Fig. 2). Mediterranean longhorn beetle (Cerambycidae) species, such as *Cerambyx welensii* (Küster, 1845) and *Niphona picticornis* Mulsant, 1839, were collected and reared from the branches of these trees, and also weevils (Curculionidae), such as *Acallobrates denticollis* (Germar, 1823), *Dodecastichus heydenii* (Stierlin, 1861) and *Otiorhynchus alutaceus* (Germar, 1817), were found here during the night.

Fig. 1. *Anelastes barbarus* P. H. Lucas, 1846 specimen from Montenegro. Scale bar = 5 mm (photo by Tamás Németh)

Fig. 2. Habitat in Montenegro, campsite 2 km S Merdari (photo by Vera Lente)

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